

Issues around managing nicotine dependence in a smoke free mental health inpatient facility (MHIF)

Introduction

The health implications of tobacco smoking have been widely acknowledged by both the medical community and the public at large for some time ^(1,2). Smoking remains the leading cause of preventable deaths worldwide and in Australia is second only to obesity. Those from low socioeconomic backgrounds tend to be disproportionately affected both in terms of tendency to smoke and smoking related disease, with those suffering from a mental illness having even higher rates ^(3,4,5). Smokers also tend to exhibit higher incidences of major mental illness ⁽⁶⁾. While smoking rates have fallen in many populations, those with a mental illness continue to smoke at high rates and specific prevention initiatives aimed at them have been minimal; they also tend to have smoked for longer ^(4,6,7). Some research suggests that staff working within mental health inpatient units have higher rates of smoking when compared to colleagues in other specialities ^(4,8). The therapeutic relationship formed between MHIF staff and consumers is however potentially useful in facilitating smoking harm reduction interventions, where staff support for such interventions can be gained ⁽⁴⁾; and where staff can be equipped with the relevant skills to deliver these interventions ⁽⁴⁾. Although society at large has moved decidedly against smoking, particularly as the harms of passive smoking have become evident, the same change has not been observed within the internal culture of mental health inpatient facilities (MHIF) ⁽⁹⁾.

Smoking within the mental health inpatient facility setting (MHIF)

Within inpatient mental health services smoking has been, and continues to be accepted ^(3,10); both as a means to pacify patients and due to perceived loss of rights issues ⁽⁵⁾. Even though not officially condoned anymore, prior to ward leave staff must distribute smoking materials to consumers and in some cases supervise patients during smoking; giving tacit approval to consumers continued smoking ⁽¹¹⁾. Disturbingly, some patients who were previously non-smokers actually take up smoking during their time on MHIF because of the extent to which smoking is part of the ward routine ^(1,12,13). Despite a high prevalence of smoking within MHIF units it has been found that a significant number of those who smoke do actually want to reduce their smoking ^(3,4,5,14), many of them making multiple attempts without much success ⁽¹⁰⁾. Evidence suggests that even if smoking is not eliminated entirely, any reduction increases the probability that future quit attempts will be successful ⁽¹²⁾; as well as lowering the chance of developing smoking related pathologies ⁽¹²⁾. Moreover, despite differing health needs due to their condition, MHIF users respond to the same treatments as the general population ⁽¹⁰⁾.

Smoking status of staff members plays a role in determining their attitude toward tobacco use ^(11,15). Smoking by staff also appears to trigger patients to smoke in some cases ^(3,4). Despite some MHIF staff valuing smoking as a therapeutic tool, research with mental health professionals shows that once a smoke-free policy is comprehensively implemented, patient care is actually easier ⁽¹¹⁾. Comprehensive implementation means that smoke free-policy is applied and enforced across all hospital departments without exception ⁽¹⁶⁾. To be effective, policy addressing smoking must include adequate interventions to manage nicotine addiction combined with education ⁽¹⁶⁾.

Most staff within MHIF believe that health care facilities should promote a healthy environment by actively discouraging smoking⁽⁴⁾. Smoke-free policy appears to lead to reductions in smoking among staff, when proper education and support is made available⁽¹¹⁾. However, it is not clear whether this effect is the same for MH patients, though when a supportive environment is made available they are also able to address smoking successfully⁽⁹⁾. A majority of hospitals both in Australia and around the world are now smoke-free⁽¹⁷⁾, despite this a culture accepting of smoking clearly exists within mental health units⁽⁴⁾.

Within MHIF emphasising the physical effects of cigarette smoking is an ineffective means of justifying elimination of the behavior, as health concerns tend to be contextualized solely in terms of how they impact mental health^(1,4,12). In some difficult to manage disorders such as schizophrenia, smoking can actually improve outcomes by affecting levels of dopamine in the brain, one of the body's "feel good" hormones⁽¹⁸⁾. This "positive" effect is however offset by a 20% shorter life expectancy of people with a diagnosis of schizophrenia and mental health patients generally, when compared to the general population⁽¹⁾. Much of this excess mortality can be attributed to the increased rates of smoking in this population⁽¹⁾. Boredom and a lack of other available pastimes also play a role in encouraging smoking^(3,14).

Barriers to smoking reduction

Smoking by staff can lead to inconsistent enforcement of smoke-free policy⁽⁵⁾, as many staff members smokers or not view limitations on smoking as being punitive in nature⁽⁵⁾. Indeed, some MHIF staff actually view smoking as important in maintaining the mental health of consumers^(3,4,5), going as far as to suggest that it is a means to manage certain emotional symptoms^(3,4,5). Obviously, this institutional reinforcement is detrimental to consumers because it contributes further to an already high prevalence⁽³⁾. At the same time, many staff feel that staff members who smoke often do not get adequate support from hospitals to address their condition⁽¹¹⁾. Little discussion regarding smoking as a health issue actually takes place between consumers and health professionals⁽⁴⁾, possibly because MHIF staff believe that smoking actually facilitates interaction between themselves and consumers in a less formal manner; which can be beneficial to care⁽⁴⁾. Additionally, some health professionals believe that MHIF consumers are uninterested or unable to manage their smoking^(5,9). Also, staff don't necessarily see it as part of their job to help consumers stop smoking⁽³⁾. For staff themselves workload, stressful work environment and shift patterns have been highlighted as one of the main barriers to smoking reduction⁽⁵⁾.

Hospitalization is a barrier in itself to addressing smoking for consumers, with research showing a greater proportion of MHIF consumers smoke when compared with those suffering from a mental disorder who live at home^(1,19). Mental illness itself appears not to be a barrier to understand the benefits of smoking reduction when adequate education is given⁽⁹⁾. However, smokers with a mental illness do demonstrate lower rates of smoking reduction initiation when compared to other population groups⁽²⁰⁾, which can most likely be attributed to chronic stress⁽⁹⁾. Smoke-free policy may have been positive in reducing some people's propensity to smoke, but MHIF consumers are now forced to smoke only during designated ward leave⁽¹¹⁾. This causes the smoking of a greater number of cigarettes in a shorter time, resulting in what is best described as binge smoking⁽¹¹⁾. Of even greater concern is the high blood nicotine and increased exposure to toxic additive chemicals caused by this phenomenon⁽¹¹⁾. Such a spike in nicotine

level is likely to make nicotine withdrawal more acute, thus increasing the urgency to smoke even more ⁽¹¹⁾. After active smoking has concluded high carbon monoxide levels persist, which affect mood and energy levels by impairing the body's ability to uptake oxygen ⁽²¹⁾. Smokers with a mental illness are described as being more "efficient" smokers than those without a mental illness, while this means they are able to absorb more nicotine from a single cigarette; it also means they are exposed to even higher levels of these toxic chemicals ⁽²²⁾.

Probably the most significant obstacle in preventing MHIF consumers from reducing smoking is the notion that consumers' "right to smoke" must be preserved ⁽⁵⁾. This stems from the fact that once inside a mental health unit many rights and freedoms normally taken for granted must be temporarily surrendered ⁽⁵⁾. Indeed, allowing consumers to smoke allows them to maintain a small amount of control over their own destiny, while taking it away is viewed by some as depriving them of their one remaining right ⁽⁵⁾. Smokers themselves are obviously firm proponents of this perceived right, even going so far as to advocate for the provision of dedicated smokers areas ⁽⁴⁾. By forcing smoking off-premises we are turning smoking into an object of conflict between consumers and staff, because consumers are not necessarily willing participants in their treatment. Therefore smoking becomes an additional form of resistance, affecting the therapeutic relationship between healthcare providers and consumers ⁽⁴⁾. This creates preoccupation among consumers as to when they will be able to smoke again ⁽⁹⁾. Consumers themselves often express anger at having their right to smoke institutionally curtailed ⁽⁷⁾, with some even going so far as to say that despite being "forced" to stop they will begin smoking again in upon discharge ^(7,23). This frustrated response to having smoking behavior limited is not only a response to perceived loss of rights by the client, it is in fact enhanced by nicotine withdrawal symptomatology ⁽²³⁾.

The possibility of having aggression directed at them by consumers is raised by staff ⁽¹⁴⁾, though this can be minimised if smoking policies are properly planned and consistently applied ^(7,11,14). This needs to be done sooner rather than later, as the ultimate goal for policy makers is that smoking will not be able to take place anywhere near hospital grounds; in addition to providing health benefits ⁽²⁾. Proper communication between policy makers and healthcare providers is necessary to ensure that tobacco control measures are properly implemented ⁽²⁴⁾. While staff are aware of these policies, they have not been given adequate training in how to apply them ⁽²⁴⁾. Despite objections, MHIF cannot reasonably be exempted from inclusion in smoke-free policy due to the increased vulnerability of those suffering from a mental illness ⁽²⁵⁾. If such an exclusion were made available then it would further exacerbate the existing health inequalities of this population ⁽²⁵⁾. Furthermore, mental health consumers already constitute a stigmatized community and exempting them from complying with smoke free policy would only serve to stigmatize them further, preventing acceptance and integration into wider society ⁽²⁵⁾.

Smoking and mental disorders

Smoking rates among those living with a mental illness are significantly higher than those of the general population ⁽¹⁾. With smoking rates of those living in psychiatric institutions being up to

70%⁽³⁾; increasing with the severity of the mental illness^(9,20). Given that many of those suffering from a mental illness are more likely to belong to the low socioeconomic bracket, also a group more likely to smoke, their risk of poor health outcomes is even higher^(3,4,5). Suicide risk may also be higher in smokers (+10%), though it is difficult to deduce whether this is to do with smoking or the other demographic factors of this population^(1,26). Importantly, addressing smoking behavior does not appear to increase the risk of suicide⁽²⁶⁾. We have already identified that smoking may reduce some of the symptoms of schizophrenia^(1,3), there is also evidence to suggest that smoking also reduces the sedating side effects of antipsychotic medication^(3,9), which many consumers find unpleasant^(1,9); a problem which affects adherence to treatment⁽¹⁾.

A prevailing myth is that smoking has a calming effect, reducing stress levels⁽⁹⁾. This is widely believed by consumers and those working in mental health, because many of the symptoms of nicotine withdrawal are also associated with mental illnesses⁽⁹⁾. The stress reduction experienced with having a cigarette is because the requirement for nicotine has been satisfied by smoking⁽⁹⁾. Therefore, the stress experienced is a symptom of nicotine withdrawal rather than being situation related or a symptom of other mental health problems^(27,28). In fact because of dependence issues, smoking actually increases stress levels overall^(9,28). Furthermore, upon reducing cigarette intake or quitting altogether individuals often report a reduction in overall stress levels^(26,27).

There is strong evidence of drug interaction with polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and a number of psychiatric medications, including antipsychotics, antidepressants and benzodiazepines^(9,29,30). With tobacco smoke accelerating the metabolism of these medications^(29,30), reduction increases the blood level and so possibly the effectiveness of these medications⁽⁹⁾. Tobacco smoke contains over 7000 other chemicals, many carcinogenic, which also interact with brain and neurotransmitter activity⁽²²⁾. It is therefore conceivable that many of these chemicals may impact on the pharmacological effect of psychiatric medications in those who do smoke⁽²²⁾. It has even been suggested that the interaction of psychiatric medications and tobacco smoke byproducts may be a source of rehospitalization for the long term mentally ill⁽²²⁾. Interaction between byproducts and medications is very much drug-specific, meaning that some medications have greater affinity to react with smoking byproducts than others⁽²⁹⁾. Even medications in the same therapeutic category can respond to the presence of these byproducts in very different ways⁽²⁹⁾. Where there are adverse drug reactions arising from the presence of smoking byproducts, the usual manifestation is a decrease in drug plasma concentration⁽²⁹⁾. This is particularly the case with antipsychotics, causing smokers to require higher doses to obtain therapeutic levels, increasing the likelihood of suffering drug-related side effects^(9,29). Giving up smoking on the other hand increases plasma concentration of medications, which may cause acute toxicity^(9,29). Addressing smoking therefore requires medication review with possible dose reduction^(9,29).

Current initiatives in Australia

Smoking harm reduction measures potentially reduce associated mortality and morbidity, particularly when initiated within an inpatient setting⁽¹⁷⁾; even when the onset of smoking related disease has begun⁽¹⁷⁾. Smoking harm reduction may take many forms including the use of nicotine patches, gum, sprays and lozenges. Collectively these treatments are referred to as

Nicotine Replacement Therapy (NRT) ⁽¹¹⁾. Pharmacotherapies also exist, such as Bupropion and Varenicline ⁽³¹⁾. Prescription of NRT may also be combined with some form of education as well as continued follow up during the support process ^(5,10,31). Both NRT and other pharmacotherapies demonstrate better outcomes when education in the effective use of products is included ^(5,10,31). Smoking behaviour can also be addressed through the provision of harm reduction strategies ⁽²⁶⁾, making the aforementioned treatments available but combining them with education; allowing smoking but realigning the emphasis to be on smoking less rather than eliminating smoking entirely ⁽²²⁾.

As nicotine dependence is a relapsing disorder ⁽¹⁰⁾, ongoing post-discharge support is necessary to sustain any change initiated in the MHIF ^(17,31); possibly for up to 6 months and beyond ^(14,31). While basic prevention information is currently given to consumers ⁽³²⁾, post-discharge follow up in the form of counselling significantly improves the sustainability of reduction efforts by consumers ^(14,31,33). Currently NRT in New South Wales is made available to hospitalized consumers to manage nicotine withdrawal ⁽¹⁷⁾. Upon admission all MHIF consumers are screened for nicotine dependence and offered NRT if necessary ⁽¹¹⁾. Outside of MHIF some of the cost of continued NRT must be borne by the individual consumer because NRT is typically offered under standard PBS arrangements; 12 weeks treatment of only one patch per day which is often insufficient for mental health consumers. Wider coverage for NRT under both public and private medical insurance is therefore needed ⁽²²⁾. NRT is typically available to inpatients free of charge, but as time spent in inpatient care is kept to an absolute minimum the utility of this free period is negligible ⁽¹⁷⁾. Providing NRT in inpatient care does however reduce the number of consumers who are discharged against medical advice, where treatment is being undergone voluntarily ⁽²⁶⁾. NRT is also safe when used concurrently with smoking, that is combining the clean nicotine of NRT products with the continued use of cigarettes; ideally at reduced frequency ⁽²²⁾.

It is important to train MHIF clinical staff how to prescribe, administer and monitor treatment for nicotine dependence ⁽²²⁾. Another problem with current NRT provision is that it is often administered to the client with inadequate education or none at all, by providers without specific training in how to correctly use the products ^(5,11). Without proper instruction in their use, this may lead to consumers using the products ineffectively; possibly affecting their perception of how useful the products actually are ⁽⁵⁾. Currently most health services are not providing this training to staff ⁽³²⁾, something which is of concern given that staff training levels have been found to directly influence the success of initiatives targeted at addressing smoking ⁽³⁴⁾. Nor do staff feel comfortable providing this treatment without adequate training ^(11,22), despite feeling that providing such treatment is as important as other activities within MHIF units ^(11,35). Some services are however beginning to recognise that for interventions to be successful it is necessary to provide support for staff who smoke as well as consumers ⁽¹¹⁾. Importantly, providing smokers with NRT and other measures to manage their nicotine dependence actually takes less time than providing individual consumers with their personal smoking materials, which for obvious safety reasons have to be locked away ^(25,35). Some clinicians erroneously believe that issuing NRT to consumers is a complex process, when in actual fact using simple “time to first cigarette” methods it is possible to provide a simplified and easy to follow therapy framework for both consumers and clinicians ⁽²²⁾. An innovative approach to addressing smoking related behaviour is to give patients a measurable perception of the health impact their smoking is

having ⁽²¹⁾. This has been done in the past through the use of a handheld device known as a CO monitor, which analyses a sample of breath to measure the level of carbon monoxide ⁽²¹⁾.

Carbon monoxide

The detrimental effects of carbon monoxide (CO) ingestion to human health are well recognized ⁽³⁶⁾. Physiologically this derives from the fact that the haemoglobin responsible for carrying oxygen in red blood cells readily binds more easily to CO than it does to oxygen ⁽³⁶⁾. If excessive levels are present this leads to acute hypoxia and death. However, there are also long term poisoning effects of chronic exposure to CO. The diminished oxygen carrying capacity caused by smoking may affect cognition, possibly exacerbating symptoms of mental disorders ⁽³⁶⁾. The effects of CO exposure persist for a significant amount of time after a smoking episode has ceased ⁽³⁶⁾. Evidence also suggests that CO greatly increases the speed at which atherosclerosis develops ⁽³⁶⁾. Therefore due to the health effects of CO, it makes sense to use CO monitoring as a method of measuring smoking behavior ⁽³⁷⁾. Research demonstrates that exhaled CO is a satisfactory marker for measuring nicotine dependence in the clinical setting ⁽³⁸⁾.

Carboxyhemoglobin levels, the amount of haemoglobin bound to CO rather than oxygen are significantly elevated in smokers ⁽³⁹⁾. Increased carboxyhemoglobin levels correlate directly with the level of CO present in exhaled air ⁽³⁹⁾. This is important because the measurement of carboxyhemoglobin levels is not clinically viable for widespread use due to the cost involved, as well as being invasive due to the need to draw blood ⁽³⁸⁾. In contrast CO monitoring is both minimally invasive and cost effective for widespread use ⁽³⁸⁾. Moreover, it gives a proper objective measure of smoking status instead of relying on biased self-report data from consumers ⁽³⁸⁾.

Conclusion

Smoking remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in New South Wales, accounting for 6000 deaths annually ⁽¹⁷⁾. While smoking may have assisted in building rapport with consumers in the past, we must now consider the wider health implications ^(3,4,5). Reluctance to address smoking related issues on the part of staff leads to failure of prevention measures in the short term, but ultimately in increased mortality and morbidity for an already disproportionately affected population ⁽¹⁾. Some of this disease burden has been addressed through the passing of smoke-free legislation ⁽⁵⁾. However, emphasis has been placed on criminalizing the behavior rather than treating it ⁽¹¹⁾. A significant shift in the culture of MHIF away from an environment favoring smoking to one less supportive of this behavior has already taken place ⁽¹¹⁾. The next step is to provide a means by which the health effects of tobacco smoking can be addressed without provoking resistance from consumers and providers ⁽⁴⁾. A majority of treatment approaches available place an emphasis on cessation rather than reduction ⁽²²⁾. Though complete cessation is the optimum outcome, reduction can still lead to significant health benefits by replacing a highly unhealthy behavior with one that is considerably less unhealthy, moving smokers along the continuum of change ⁽²⁶⁾. Moreover, MHIF consumers face a number of unique circumstances which make reduction more attainable than complete elimination ^(3,5,10). Additionally, given that a significant proportion of mental health providers think that consumers should not be forced to quit, a reduction strategy is a more feasible alternative ⁽¹¹⁾. We must also teach smokers to recognize the symptoms of nicotine withdrawal, and educate them to manage these symptoms with clean nicotine products (NRT) rather than with cigarettes ⁽⁵⁾. If MHIF staff

are brought on board and are also smokers, it may be possible to replace the therapeutic relationship developed through shared smoking into shared smoking reduction ⁽⁴⁾. Therefore, staff must be empowered in their health promotion role to correctly deliver NRT ^(11,22). This can be reinforced through the use of CO monitoring in conjunction with NRT, to give a measurable impression to consumers of the detrimental effects of smoking on their health ⁽³⁸⁾. What needs to happen is for smoking to be contextualized as the chronic dependence disorder that it is, so that more active multi-component interventions can be undertaken which are sustainable in the long term ⁽¹⁷⁾. Finally, interventions need to include strategies to support staff who smoke, and provide ongoing training in the management of patient's nicotine dependence ⁽¹¹⁾.

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